

EFFECTIVE TENSILE STRENGTH OF ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER VIA COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The initial phase of extrusion-based additive manufacturing (AM) methods like fused layer manufacturing (FLM), fused deposition modeling (FDMTM), and fused filament fabrication (FFF) is characterized by prototyping. Due to improvements in technology, process, and material such as reinforcing the polymer, applications change to manufacturing final parts. The aim of this study is a detailed comprehension of process-related characteristics and the corresponding influence on the composite. Hence, a discontinuous carbon fiber-reinforced semi-aromatic polyamide (CarbonXTM Nylon, 3DXTECH, USA) was applied. The filament has a fiber content of 12.5 wt.-%, the fiber diameter is 7 μm by a typical length of fibers between 150 and 400 μm after fabrication to filaments. Separating process-related characteristics of FLM, reference specimens were fabricated via injection molding (IM) with single-batch material. Quasi-static tensile tests were executed for mechanical characterization. Void volume content and void distribution were analyzed via micro-computed tomography (CT). In further processing steps, micro-CT data were investigated by image processing receiving the void area share in the cross-sectional area. Taking the adapted cross-sectional area into account, the effective tensile strength of additively manufactured composite is calculated.

The investigations show higher tensile strength, lower void content and smaller standard deviation of IM specimens compared to FLM. Process-related characteristics of FLM result in an alignment of voids in dependency of printing direction and a volume void content up to 6.5%. The adjustment of the cross-sectional area influences the tensile strength positively by an increased effective tensile strength up to 14%.

1 INTRODUCTION

The additive manufacturing (AM) techniques fused deposition modeling (FDMTM), fused filament fabrication (FFF) and fused layer manufacturing (FLM) are all based on material extrusion and one of the most widely used AM methods [1]. The early period of these technologies is characterized by prototyping or tooling. Besides, combining the advantages of AM like an integration of features, load tailored design, and resource efficiency leads to holistic optimization. The continuous improvements in technology, process, and material change the main application to serial parts. Producing serial parts require a deep understanding of the manufacturing process and the influence of process-related characteristics on the composite. These include for example the anisotropy and void dependency in the printing direction. Unfortunately, there is no standard, guideline or restriction for a consistent determination of material characteristics of polymer-based AM parts [1-4].

Nevertheless, a large number of publications deal with the mechanical characterization of additively manufactured parts [5-8]. Dawoud et al. [9] characterized the mechanical properties of polymers produced via FDMTM and injection molding (IM). The results show a general trend of higher tensile strength of IM specimens, because of the higher compaction compared to FDMTM specimens. Floor et

al. [10] made a systematic parameter study of additively manufactured polymer. The significant influence of voids was recognized and included in the study. The void content was estimated by weighing the specimens. Miller et al. [11] investigated the additively manufactured specimens by micro-computed tomography (CT) receiving void content and void distribution.

In this study, quality assessment is based on micro-CT data as well. In further processing steps, the micro-CT data are used for determining the effective tensile strength. Therefore, the influence of parameters on void content and void distribution is investigated. The effective cross-sectional area determined by micro-CT and additional image processing via MATLAB (MathWorks, USA) is used for the effective tensile strength of discontinuous carbon fiber-reinforced polymer. The approach of separating the material testing and process-related characteristics aims to increase the comprehension of material extrusion and enable a combination of designing guidelines.

2 MATERIAL AND MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

2.1 Material

A discontinuous carbon fiber-reinforced polyamide (CarbonX™ Nylon, 3DXTECH, USA) is investigated. The material is delivered as filament with 2.85 mm in diameter on vacuumed spools. The composite has a fiber weight content of approx. 12.5 wt.-%, a fiber diameter of 7 μm and the fiber length is between 150 and 400 μm . The filament is intended for use within a commercial FLM system so that the filament can be processed without modifications. Ensuring single-batch reference specimens via IM, the filament had to be crushed in approx. 4 mm granulate. Before processing with both manufacturing techniques, the material is dried by 50°C for 4 hours in an oven (FP 115, Binder, Germany).

2.2 Injection molding (IM)

Comparing FLM specimens, reference specimens are manufactured with an IM system (Arburg 320C, Arburg, Germany). The shape of tooling used for production, including a mold flow analysis is illustrated in Fig. 1. Considering the corresponding flow fronts due to two mold gates, specimen 1 and 2 have a weld line which acts as a predetermined breaking point. In contrast, specimen 3 is filled homogeneously thru one mold gate forming no predetermined breaking point within the testing area. Hence, for following investigations just specimen 3 is used. In Table 1 selected manufacturing parameters of the IM system are given.

Figure 1: Injection molding tooling with corresponding mold flow analysis.

Parameter	Unit	CarbonX™
Dosage volume	cm^3	7
Screw temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	270
Injection flow	$\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	35
Residual cooling time	s	8
Injection pressure	bar	1000
Back pressure	bar	250

Table 1: Selected manufacturing parameters for IM specimens.

2.3 Fused layer manufacturing (FLM)

The specimens are manufactured additively with a FLM system (Ultimaker 2+ Extended, Ultimaker BV, Netherlands) focusing on three different manufacturing orientations. Figure 2 displays the manufacturing orientations of FLM specimens, the specified angle gives the printing direction in the relation to the loading direction. 0° and 90° specimens are generated flat on the build platform (xy-plane), the Z specimens stand upright. Each specimen was fabricated directly on the build platform out of glass, which was cleaned in a pre-process with acetone. Table 2 gives an overview of manufacturing parameters for FLM specimens.

Figure 2: Manufacturing orientations of FLM specimens.

Parameter	Unit	CarbonX™
Nozzle diameter	mm	0.4
Extrusion width	mm	0.5
Layer height	mm	0.2
Manufacturing orientation	-	0° , 90° , Z
Extruder temperature	$^\circ\text{C}$	260
Printing speed	$\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$	30

Table 2: Selected manufacturing parameters for FLM specimens.

2.4 Quality assessment

In consideration of quality assessment, all specimens were investigated in a two-stage process, consisting out of micro-CT scans, determining quantity and distribution of voids as well as a comparison of specimens' weight. Micro-CT scans were carried out on a micro-CT system (XT H 160, Nikon, Japan), weighing specimens was done by a high-resolution scale (AB204, Mettler-Toledo, USA).

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Quasi-static tensile tests were carried out at a universal testing system (Zwick 1464, $F_{\max} = 50 \text{ kN}$) following DIN 527-1. The specimen geometry according to DIN 527-2 is given in Fig. 3. Strain measurements of the entire tests were done by a tactile extensometer (MultiXtens, Zwick, Germany). To ensure similar climatic conditions, all specimens were stored in standard atmosphere according to DIN 527-1 at 23°C and 50% relative humidity for 24 hours (KMF, 240, Binder, Germany). After preloading with 10 N, Young's modulus was determined in a range of 0.05% to 0.25% total strain at a displacement speed of $1 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. For determining the tensile strength the displacement speed was switched to $50 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The tests were stopped at 50% drop in force. Acoustic emissions were monitored by high-frequency impulse measurements (HFIM) (Optimzer4D, Qass, Germany). The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 5: Nominal tensile stress σ_n vs. total strain ϵ_t diagrams for a) IM, b) 0° , c) 90° , d) Z specimens.

The bar chart in Fig. 6 summarizes the Young's modulus (E), ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}) as well as the mass (m) of all variations. The values show the average and the corresponding standard deviation of each test series with $n = 5$. The reference specimens fabricated via IM have the highest mass and smallest standard deviation ($1,705 \pm 3 \text{ mg}$). All additively manufactured specimens show lower masses; $1561 \pm 3 \text{ mg}$ (0° specimens), $1548 \pm 5 \text{ mg}$ (90° specimens), and $1610 \pm 15 \text{ mg}$ (Z specimens).

Figure 6: Young's modulus E , tensile strength σ_{UTS} , and mass m for IM, 0° , 90° and Z specimens.

Figure 7 gives a representative example for 3D-models out of micro-CT scans for all variations. Inside the IM specimen shown in Fig. 7a, no voids are visible. The 0° and 90° specimens exhibit a uniform distribution of voids with nearly similar void volume. A detailed view clarifies a dependency of void orientation and printing direction as well as a primary occurrence between two extrusion beads in xy-plane and two layers in the Z direction. This results in void volume contents of 6.5% (0°), 4.8% (90°), and 4.7% (Z). The Z specimen shows higher defect volume per void and an unsteady void distribution with concentrations of larger voids between the layers.

Figure 7: 3D-models including void analysis and void distribution by micro-CT for a) IM, b) 0°, c) 90° and d) Z specimen.

5 IMAGE PROCESSING

The 3D-models of micro-CT scans in Fig. 7 demonstrate that a statement based on the void volume content is not sufficient to describe the additively manufactured results. Similar void volume contents of 4.8% (90° specimen) and 4.7% (Z specimen) show different appearances in the material through un-

Figure 8: Exemplary 2D-cross-sectional area out of micro-CT scan of a 0° specimen, a) original micro-CT data, b) binary image after image processing.

even distribution. Furthermore, the distribution of volume can lead to a varying distribution of void area within a particular cross-section. Hence, 2D-cross-sectional areas of the micro-CT scans are analyzed through MATLAB receiving the effective area of material and void. Converting the original picture of the micro-CT scan (Fig. 8a) in a binary image (Fig. 8b) it is possible to calculate the percentage of material and void area, resulting in the effective cross-sectional area of the specimen. This procedure is executed for five random cross-sectional areas within the specimens' testing area calculating mean and corresponding standard deviation. The results of void volume content and void area share are summarized in Fig. 9.

Including the void area share in the calculation of ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}), the initial cross-section is changed. The reduced cross-section leads to an increased effective tensile strength (σ_{EFF}). The results of ultimate tensile strength and adapted effective tensile strength are compared in the bar chart in Fig. 9. The effective tensile strength is increased for 0° specimens about 14%, 90° specimens about 11%, and for Z specimens about 3% compared to ultimate tensile strength. For the IM specimen with approx. 0% void volume content, the ultimate tensile strength and effective tensile strength are the same.

Figure 9: Ultimate tensile strength, effective tensile strength, volume void content, and void area share for IM, 0° , 90° and Z specimen.

6 DISCUSSION

Reference specimens were fabricated with IM under high injection pressure of 1,000 bar resulting in high quality specimens with a void volume content of approx. 0% and high mechanical properties with low standard deviations. The FLM specimens have void volume contents up to 6.5%, which can explain the reduced Young's modulus and tensile strength. Especially, Z specimens, which are characterized by interlayer tensile strength, show deteriorated mechanical properties. An undefined manufacturing pressure and polymer compaction during fabrication could be one opportunity for the high void volume content and low interlayer tensile strength compared to reference specimens. So increasing polymer compaction could optimize quality and mechanical properties of FLM specimens.

Comparing the void content and mass of the specimens a relation can be observed. IM specimens have the highest mass, show the lowest void content and lower standard deviation. This indicates a reproducible manufacturing process. FLM specimens have lower masses and higher void content. The higher standard deviations demonstrate a manufacturing process which is more unstable compared to IM.

Within the FLM test series the 0° specimens have the highest mechanical properties compared to 90° and Z specimens. Furthermore, the micro-CT scans show a dependency of void orientation and printing direction. The orientation of voids is primary in printing direction within xy-plane and between two layers in Z direction. Other researchers found out that additively manufactured parts yield in printing

direction a very high fiber orientation [7] and an alignment of molecular orientation of polymers [12]. Both generally strengthen mechanical properties of composites and can explain the reduced mechanical properties within the FLM test series of 90° and Z specimen compared to 0° specimen. Furthermore, this results in a highly anisotropic mechanical behavior of additively manufactured polymers.

Micro-CT scans show that void volume contents form different shapes in 2D-cross-sectional areas. In spite of macroscopic similar cross-sectional areas, the microscopic effective cross-section is different depending on manufacturing technique and parameters. Using the effective cross-sectional area for the calculation of tensile strength is an approach to separate process-related characteristics from material testing. Based on this approach the effective tensile strength of additively manufactured composite is up to 89% of the ultimate tensile strength of quasi-homogeneous IM. The approach of reducing the cross-sectional area depending on the void area share approximates the true values more precise. However, there is a gap between the reference specimen and the additively manufactured polymer. This indicates that the approach does not consider all relevant effects like stress concentrations originating from the voids or the boundary effects between layers or extrusion beads.

7 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

For describing process-related characteristics of fused layer manufacturing (FLM) different parameter settings of a discontinuous carbon-fiber reinforced polyamide were investigated. As reference, injection molding (IM) specimens manufactured out of single-batch material were used. Mechanical investigations show higher tensile strength, lower void content and smaller standard deviation of IM specimens compared to FLM. Process-related characteristics of FLM result in an alignment of voids depending on printing direction and a void content up to 6.5%. The quality assessment is based on micro-CT data and expanded by image processing to determine the effective tensile strength. The adjustment of calculation influences the tensile strength positively by an increase in effective tensile strength up to 14%.

The mechanical characterization of additively manufactured composites shows a highly anisotropic material behavior. The printing direction Z is highlighted as weakness and should be optimized for a better overall performance of AM parts. One opportunity is an increased understanding of manufacturing pressure. A higher interlayer polymer compression during manufacturing should affect the void volume content and the interlayer bonding quality positively. This adaption should strengthen mechanical properties in Z direction and thus the overall performance.

The results of the quasi-static tensile tests increase the comprehension of FLM. Knowing the weakness of resulting material behavior can serve as a guideline for designing and adapting an AM part to an individual application. The quasi-static tensile tests will be extended with cyclic tests for an estimation of lifetime and a description of fatigue behavior for additively manufactured composites.

The void volume content and void area share were estimated in unloaded specimens. In further investigations, the micro-CT data will be collected in situ under loaded specimens. Thereby, the deformation behavior of void volume content and void area share under loading as well as failure initialization will be characterized. Furthermore, the transformation of micro-CT data and binary picture via MATLAB interface will be adapted for a more precise detection of voids.

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